

USING MODERN INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES TO INCREASE THE MOTIVATION OF STUDENT GIRLS FOR PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND SPORTS

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Abstract: the article discusses the use of information technology capabilities, in particular Smart mobile applications, in order to motivate students to engage in physical education and introduce them to a healthy lifestyle.

Keywords: digital technologies, information environment, mobile applications, health,, students

The most acute problem facing modern higher education is the deterioration of health among students. Questions about the expediency of improving the curricula of higher educational institutions by giving them a wellness orientation, including using computer programs, are considered in the works of many authors [1,2,4,5]. In their opinion, computer programs used in the practice of physical education and sports are classified into groups:

- training programs aimed at professional training of fitness specialists;
- computer programs that ensure the operation of fitness centers;
- software for working on simulators.

Undoubtedly, the rapid development of computer and digital technologies was the logical result of the development of science and society. The Internet has gained incredible popularity all over the world due to the speed of information processing and data transmission. The number of Internet users is growing rapidly and constantly, mainly due to mobile devices.

In the world, more than 90% of users access the Internet from a smartphone, and more than 80% do it daily. In our country, more than 50% use the Internet via a smartphone, and 16% use only mobile Internet. All over the world, people spend 7 times more time in mobile applications than in desktop computers.

A mobile application is a software product that allows you to find the easiest solutions to problems and save time. According to their purpose, they are divided into various categories: games, news applications, for working with photos, text, helping to conduct business, make online purchases, as well as to monitor their physical condition.

So, mobile apps for assessing motor activity track indicators such as the number of kilometers traveled, steps, calories spent, heart rate, number of approaches, total weight lifted, duration of exercises.

They help to use knowledge in the field of physical culture, offer ready-made sets of exercises and training sessions.

Programs containing sets of exercises, methodical instructions clearly show the results obtained during the training.

Mobile devices can be used in the learning process. Training involves familiarization with large amounts of information, and this information can be drawn from the network by using a mobile device. In the learning process, you can use educational portals, as well as virtual libraries, where you can find all the necessary information in electronic format. When all sources of information are always with you, it is both convenient and effective.

In addition to books, video tutorials are also used in the learning process [6,7]. Mobile devices, as tablets, for example, reproduce video material very well, so you can also use video format lessons in the learning process.

The possibilities of using mobile devices in the educational process directly in the classroom include the following: a camera - a means of recording information, Internet access to search engines, e-mail, groups in social networks, the school information and educational environment, etc.

According to researchers in the field of digital technologies, the interest of users has noticeably shifted from smartphones and tablets towards wearable technologies (Smart watches, glasses, fitness bracelets and ECG T-shirts are not items from the realm of fiction). Wearable devices, or wearables, have become a real tech trend: they are produced by both young startups and giants like Apple and Hyundai, by 2023 the rapid development of wearable electronic devices such as watches, bracelets and smart clothes is expected.

The use of mobile digital devices for educational purposes, subject to their controlled use, makes it possible to make classes interactive, allows you to improvise, reduces the negative from the prohibition of their use.

Almost all teachers face the problem of immersing students in the information flow, which is formed using mobile devices, and not for educational purposes, and very often during classes.

However, if you correctly use mobile devices in the learning process, then they can transform from "irritants" into a tool for accessing information necessary for conducting a lesson.

In turn, this allows them to more productively carry out the development of their respective competencies, to immerse themselves in the digital information environment in a controlled manner. In later life, these skills will help them acquire knowledge throughout their lives [3,4].

When choosing a mobile application for training, you should adhere to certain criteria for its selection:

1. Determine your own goal in using the application and select the most appropriate functions in the application to achieve your goals.

2. Pay attention to the popularity of the mobile application in question, according to the reviews of other users.

3. Compare user reviews with the description of the application by the developer.

4. The presence of a user-friendly interface and registration. The application should be as user-friendly as possible for a particular user, and combine the most necessary number of tools and methods to achieve the goals of a particular user.

5. The ability to individualize the application, adjust it to your criteria, for individual selection of the training program.

6. The ability to save data in the cloud when you lose access to the application and sync with other applications.

Conclusion. The use of mobile applications in the physical culture and wellness sphere can be recommended in practice as a means of:

1. Interactive learning through the transfer of basic knowledge of various training programs, motor actions. Storage of methodological programs in electronic form.

2. Control, correction of the results of motor activity.
3. Optimization of testing processes of the physical and mental state of the student.
4. Implementation of operational collection and processing of information about private motor activity, including the current state and dynamics of data.

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